

A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN 0.2% ROPIVACAINE WITH CLONIDINE AND 0.125% LEVOBUPIVACAINE WITH CLONIDINE FOR POSTOPERATIVE EPIDURAL ANALGESIA IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING TOTAL ABDOMINAL HYSTERECTOMY

Vignesh M¹, Jothi N², Revathy S³

1. Post Graduate, Department of Anaesthesiology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre

2. Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre

3. Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre

**Corresponding Author : Vignesh M*

Abstract

Background: When compared to opioid-based analgesia following a hysterectomy, epidural local anesthetics (LA) provide effective pain reduction and improved GI motility. In postoperative epidural analgesia, ropivacaine, a novel amide local anesthetic, offers less tendency of a motor block with fewer adverse effects on the central nervous system and cardiovascular system. Levobupivacaine also an amide local anesthetic which provides less CVS and CNS toxicity resembles actions of bupivacaine in terms of onset, quality, and duration of sensory block. So, this study is an attempt to determine the onset of analgesia, duration of analgesia, Hemodynamic variables, VAS Score, and adverse effects.

Material and Methods: A prospective study was done to compare ropivacaine and Levobupivacaine efficacy when combined with clonidine in patients undergoing the surgery of Total Abdominal Hysterectomy in a tertiary care center. The thirty participants were randomized to each group, and their time of onset, duration of analgesia, and hemodynamic parameters were observed and tabulated for analysis.

Results: The mean time of onset was 11.07 ± 0.466 and 8.96 ± 0.449 minutes in Group RC and LC respectively. The average duration of analgesia in Group RC was 210.07 ± 2.84 minutes, which shows a lower duration compared with Group LC, which had a longer duration (271.2 ± 2.427) of analgesia during postoperative TAH. The mean VAS score was remarkably higher in Group RC compared with LC during two, three, four, five, and six hours of post-operative analgesia.

Conclusion: Levobupivacaine provides better post-operative analgesia with a shorter time of onset and longer duration with the combination of clonidine in Total Abdominal hysterectomy surgeries when compared with Ropivacaine.

Keywords: Clonidine, Ropivacaine, Levobupivacaine, TAH, Epidural Analgesia

Introduction

The most frequent major non-obstetric surgical surgery carried out on Indian women is the total abdominal hysterectomy (TAH), which is linked with an abundance of postoperative pain and significant nausea, vomiting, and decreased gastrointestinal motility.⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾ The use of epidural analgesia in patients with TAH has been widespread, except for individuals with elevated intracranial pressure, coagulopathy, patient resistance, local infections, inability to remain still during needle puncture, and little experience.⁽³⁾ When compared to patients who received oral and intravenous opioid-based therapy, studies using epidural administration during abdominal hysterectomy for benign illness have revealed lower mean pain scores, reduced morphine use, quicker recovery of bowel function, and improved patient satisfaction.⁽⁴⁾

Clonidine is an alpha 2-adrenergic agonist, an adjuvant in regional anesthesia, that induces analgesia through a nonopioid mechanism. An agonist of both imidazoline and alpha-adrenergic receptors, clonidine has been used as an antihypertensive drug for 40 years.⁽⁵⁾ There are alpha2-adrenergic receptors on peripheral nerve endings, in the spinal cord, and the brainstem. They likely exert their primary analgesic activity in the spinal cord, where they act presynaptically on thin afferents through inhibiting transmitter release and postsynaptically by intervening with NO-mechanisms and protein kinases as well as by stimulating cholinergic interneurons.⁽⁶⁾ The use of a 150 µg dose of epidural clonidine did not provide sufficient postoperative pain relief and instead resulted in hypotension among patients undergoing abdominal hysterectomy.⁽⁷⁾ Better analgesia was produced when clonidine and

local anesthetic were administered together than when either drug was used alone.⁽⁸⁾ When compared to opioid-based analgesia following hysterectomy, epidural local anesthetics (LA) provide effective pain reduction and improved GI motility.⁽²⁾

Ropivacaine, a novel amide local anesthetic provides less tendency of motor lock with lesser cardiovascular and central nervous system toxicity in post-operative epidural analgesia. Levobupivacaine also an amide local anesthetic which provides less CVS and CNS toxicity resembles actions of bupivacaine in terms of onset, quality and duration of sensory block.⁽⁹⁾

It has clinical effects by generating a time-dependent, voltage-gated blockage of open sodium channels in neurons. Levobupivacaine works to anesthetize and relieve pain by preventing sensory and nociceptive nerve fibers from reaching the central nervous system. Additionally, these effects cause different motor nerves to become inhibited. Epidural Levobupivacaine 1.136 mg/mL provided analgesia more effectively than did levobupivacaine 0.568 mg/mL, according to clinical investigations, and it was discovered that increasing the dosage from 0.625 to 1.25 mg/mL enhanced analgesic efficacy without increasing patient satisfaction.⁽¹⁰⁾ In epidural anaesthesia and analgesia, the addition of supplementary drugs (epinephrine, opioids, or clonidine) to levobupivacaine may result in a dose-sparing effect and prolong and improve the quality of analgesia.⁽¹¹⁾ So, this study was aimed to evaluate the effect of 0.2% ropivacaine with clonidine versus 0.125% levobupivacaine with clonidine in patients undergoing total abdominal hysterectomy.

Objectives

- **PRIMARY OBJECTIVE**

- To assess the duration of post-operative analgesia of 0.2% ropivacaine with clonidine versus 0.125% levobupivacaine with clonidine in patients undergoing total abdominal hysterectomy.

- **SECONDARY OBJECTIVES**

- To determine the onset of analgesia, Hemodynamic variables, VAS Score, and adverse effects of 0.2% ropivacaine with clonidine versus 0.125% levobupivacaine with clonidine in patients undergoing total abdominal hysterectomy.

- To compare the onset of analgesia, Hemodynamic variables, VAS Score, and adverse effects of 0.2% ropivacaine with clonidine versus 0.125% levobupivacaine with clonidine in patients undergoing total abdominal hysterectomy.

Material and Methods

A Randomised controlled study was done at Department of OG, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Institute for nine months (June 2023 – February 2024) duration among patients undergoing Total abdominal hysterectomy under epidural anesthesia. The patients of ASA 1 and ASA 2 between 35 -65 years undergoing total abdominal hysterectomy were included in this study. Patients with coagulation abnormalities, renal and hepatic insufficiencies and history of drug allergy to local anesthetics were excluded from the study.

An earlier study by Anusha et al⁽⁹⁾ [2022] has shown that heart rate at 6 hours for the patients who have been given 0.2%ropivaicaine with clonidine {79.44±5.97} was significantly low compared to the heart rate of patients who have been given 0.125%levobupivaicaine with clonidine {86.12±8.5}. The adequate sample size to detect statistical significance difference at a 5% level of significance with 90% power was 30 per group. Therefore, a total of sixty patients were recruited according to inclusion and exclusion criteria and randomized into a 1:1 ratio (30 per group) by convenient sampling method. The simple randomization method was used to randomize the participants. The selected participants were requested to take lots named as Group RC and Group LC from an envelope. They were blinded to which group they belonged to. Double blinding was chosen, the participants and the observer were blinded for this study.

Local anesthetics and adjuvants administered into the epidural space for cessation of pain are known as epidural analgesia. ⁽¹²⁾ Epidural analgesia is a term that denotes an intense blockade of local anesthetics in the epidural space that may be utilized as the main anesthetic for surgery. Providing epidural analgesia is an appealing way to reduce the need for opioids while still providing great analgesia (particularly with movement), helping patients recover after surgery. ⁽¹³⁾ The time from when the study medicine was administered till when the perception of pain occurred was used to characterize the duration of analgesia. ⁽¹⁴⁾

The study protocol was approved by institutional Ethical Committee and patients were also given their informed written consent for the participation of the study. The pre-anesthetic assessment was completed the day before the procedure. Informed written consent was received from patients after they were informed about the goal of the study and trained to use the visual analogue scale (VAS) to measure their level of pain. Preloading of fluids, monitoring, and technique of epidural anesthesia was standardized for all patients. The patient was moved to the post-operative ward once the case was finished, and when the pain started, an epidural top up using the study medications was administered. Epidural blockade was done as per routine standard technique with drug volume according to groups. Post epidural first evaluation of the intensity of pain was done by the visual analogue scale and when the pain scores touch more than five, the intended drugs were given through an epidural catheter. Group RC received 10ml 0.2% ropivacaine and clonidine 1mcg / kg. Group LC received 10ml 0.125% levobupivacaine and clonidine 1mcg / kg. Heart rate, blood pressure, onset of analgesia, duration of analgesia, and VAS Score are measured every 15 minutes for the first 1 hour and thereafter every 1 hour for the next 5 hours. For the first 60 minutes following the drug's administration, the hemodynamic parameters were continually evaluated, and any deviations from the baseline value of 20% or more were treated. Intravenous atropine injection was used to treat bradycardia, which was defined as a heart rate of less than 60 beats per minute or a reduction of more than 20% from baseline readings. Heart rates greater than 100 beats per minute were considered tachycardia, and a mean arterial blood pressure drop of more than 20 percent from baseline was considered hypotension. Both conditions were treated with an intravenous bolus injection of mephentermine (6 mg). The visual analogue scale consists from 0 – 10 scale readings suggest that no pain to severe pain respectively. The data was presented as percentages or as mean + standard deviation. The statistical studies were all carried out on Windows using "Microsoft Excel 2010" and SPSS software version 2021. The monitored and computed parameters were analyzed using the Student's Unpaired t-test with the statistical significance of p-value less than 0.05.

Results

The mean age of participants in Group RC was 43.33 ± 8.159 years and in Group LC was 52.57 ± 4.932 years. The Group RC participants were reported with a mean height of 155.23 ± 5.728 cms, mean weight of 63.43 ± 4.4 kgs, and mean BMI of 26.42 ± 2.62 kg/m². The Group LC participants were reported with a mean height of 156.07 ± 4.472 cms, mean weight

of 63.8 ± 4.221 kgs, and mean BMI of 26.25 ± 2.35 kg/m^2 . The mean height ($p = 0.532$), mean weight ($p = 0.743$), and BMI ($p = 0.797$) had no difference among both groups.

Figure 1 shows the time of onset in both groups. The mean time of onset was 11.07 ± 0.466 and 8.96 ± 0.449 minutes in Group RC and LC respectively. The mean duration of analgesia in Group RC was 210.07 ± 2.84 minutes, which shows a lower duration compared with Group LC, which had a longer duration (271.2 ± 2.427) of analgesia during postoperative TAH. Figure 2 shows the duration of analgesia in both groups.

The statistical significance of the duration of analgesia and Time of onset was determined as significant ($p < 0.05$) based on the Student T test.

Table 1: Comparison of onset and duration of analgesia in both groups				
S No	Variables	Group RC (n = 30)	Group LC (n = 30)	p-value
1	Time of onset	11.07±0.466	8.96±0.449	0.001
2	Duration of analgesia	210.07±2.84	271.2±2.427	0.001

The heart rate was maintained stable in both groups, but the heart rate was higher in Group LC compared with Group RC, whereas this difference was found to be statistically significant.

Table 2: Comparison of heart rate in both groups				
S No	Heart rate	Group RC (n = 30)	Group LC (n = 30)	p-value
1	Baseline	78.97±4.437	87±4.394	0.001
2	15 minutes	76.3±5.23	86.43±5.177	0.001
3	30 minutes	73.23±4.797	84.7±5.478	0.001
4	45 minutes	72.5±4.108	83.7±5.318	0.001
5	60 minutes	73.1±4.574	83.47±5.655	0.001
6	2 hours	74.87±4.321	81.97±6.054	0.001
7	3 hours	77.43±3.66	83±4.79	0.001
8	4 hours	77.77±3.38	86.5±4.142	0.001
9	5 hours	77.3±3.25	87.23±3.748	0.001
10	6 hours	78.37±2.95	86.97±4.255	0.001

Figure 3 shows the line diagram of the mean heart rate among both groups based on duration.

The systolic blood pressure was maintained stable in both groups, and it was found to be significantly higher in Group RC compared with Group LC up to two hours postoperative epidural analgesia.

S No	Systolic blood pressure	Group RC (n = 30)	Group LC (n = 30)	p-value
1	Baseline	129.13±3.589	125.5±4.652	0.001
2	15 minutes	119.97±4.351	115.5±5.84	0.001
3	30 minutes	113.97±4.414	113.60±5.99	0.001
4	45 minutes	115.13±5.97	110.4±4.67	0.001
5	60 minutes	115.93±1.982	110.4±2.81	0.001
6	2 hours	115.47±1.57	113.87±3.821	0.038
7	3 hours	116.2±4.12	118.7±4.55	0.030
8	4 hours	115.97±4.351	119.57±3.36	0.001
9	5 hours	114.63±3.672	119.33±3.05	0.001
10	6 hours	117.43±2.96	121.67±3.67	0.001

Figure 4 shows the line diagram of mean systolic blood pressure among both groups based on duration.

The diastolic blood pressure was stable during post-operative analgesia in both groups, but it showed a significantly higher increase during two, four, and five hours of postoperative analgesia in Group LC compared with Group RC. Table 4 describes the comparison of diastolic blood pressure in both groups.

S No	Diastolic blood pressure	Group RC (n = 30)	Group LC (n = 30)	p-value
1	Baseline	79.87±3.739	78.63±6.009	0.344
2	15 minutes	76.6±3.62	75.43±5.39	0.330
3	30 minutes	76.3±4.103	75.43±5.46	0.487
4	45 minutes	76.27±4.042	74.47±5.46	0.153
5	60 minutes	75.43±3.73	75.01±4.74	0.696
6	2 hours	74.37±3.44	77.9±4.46	0.001
7	3 hours	76.5±3.35	78±4.16	0.155
8	4 hours	77.93±3.99	82.2±2.172	0.001
9	5 hours	77.27±3.629	80.47±4.075	0.002
10	6 hours	78.9±3.56	78.5±3.422	0.659

Figure 5 shows the variation in mean diastolic blood pressure in both groups.

There was a significant increase in mean arterial pressure in Group LC during two, four, and five hours of postoperative analgesia compared with Group RC. Table 5 describes the comparison of Mean arterial pressure in both groups.

S No	Mean arterial pressure	Group RC (n = 30)	Group LC (n = 30)	p-value
1	Baseline	96.28±3.56	94.25±4.93	0.072
2	15 minutes	91.05±3.44	88.78±3.65	0.016
3	30 minutes	88.85±2.88	88.15±3.88	0.432
4	45 minutes	87.64±3.26	88.02±5.13	0.735
5	60 minutes	88.93±2.61	86.8±3.64	0.012
6	2 hours	88.06±2.44	89.88±3.88	0.034
7	3 hours	89.73±3.12	91.56±4.18	0.059
8	4 hours	90.61±3.84	94.65±2.07	0.001
9	5 hours	89.72±3.2	93.42±2.73	0.002
10	6 hours	91.74±3.05	92.88±3.14	0.158

Figure 6 shows the variation in mean VAS score in groups.

Table 6 describes the comparison of VAS scores in both groups. The mean VAS score was significantly higher in Group RC compared with LC during two, three, four, five, and six hours of post-operative analgesia.

S No	VAS score	Group RC (n = 30)	Group LC (n = 30)	p-value
1	Baseline	5.47±0.507	5.47±0.507	1
2	15 minutes	0.20±0.407	0.13±0.346	0.497
3	30 minutes	0.40±0.498	0.30±0.466	0.425
4	45 minutes	0.60±0.498	0.50±0.509	0.445
5	60 minutes	1.23±0.568	1.03±0.850	0.289
6	2 hours	1.50±0.509	1.17±0.379	0.003
7	3 hours	1.57±0.504	1.1±0.305	0.001
8	4 hours	2.60±0.498	2.3±0.466	0.019
9	5 hours	2.93±0.583	2.5±0.509	0.003
10	6 hours	3.77±0.43	2.80±0.61	0.001

Figure 7 shows the reported adverse effects in both groups. The adverse events like Nausea, vomiting, urinary retention was observed equally in both groups. Shivering and dizziness reported more in Group RC compared with Group LC.

Discussion

This trial was conducted to determine the post-operative analgesia in two groups, namely Clonidine versus Levobupivacaine and Clonidine versus Ropivacaine.

Time of onset

Our study describes that the mean time of onset was 11.07 ± 0.466 and 8.96 ± 0.449 minutes in Group RC and LC respectively. Anusha T al(9) reported that the comparison between group LD (levobupivacaine 0.125+dexmedetomidine) and group RD (ropivacaine 0.125+dexmedetomidine) showed mean onset of analgesia (11.86 mins vs 8.47 mins) was substantially higher for TAH surgeries in group LD which shows similar results. Sharma M et al(15) found that among lower abdominal surgeries ropivacaine added with fentanyl provides 5 – 10 minutes of onset among 70% of individuals. However, the use of levobupivacaine with fentanyl provides earlier onset (5 – 10 minutes) among 50% of individuals.

Duration of analgesia

Our study found that the mean duration of analgesia in Group RC was 210.07 ± 2.84 minutes, which shows a lower duration compared with Group LC, which had a longer duration (271.2 ± 2.427) of analgesia during postoperative TAH. Sharma M et al(15) found that the mean duration of analgesia was 276 ± 30.8 min among patients with ropivacaine and 259 ± 20.95 in among patients with levobupivacaine combined with fentanyl. Chandrakant et al(14) reported that the mean duration of analgesia was greater in the Levobupivacaine group (471.75 ± 43.494 mins) compared with ropivacaine (421.5 ± 26.047 min) when administered among the pediatric age group for infra umbilical surgeries along with clonidine. Anusha T al(9) reported that group LD had greater the mean duration of analgesia (271.52 mins vs 210.04 mins) in group LD compared with group RD. Chandrakant et al(14) and Anusha T al(9) found similar results of study irrespective of surgeries and adjuncts used for analgesia. Sharma M et al(15) reported longer duration of analgesia in Ropivacaine group, could be due to use of fentanyl and concentration of levobupivacaine.

Babu S et al(16) showed that the mean duration of analgesia was longer in the RD group (ropivacaine + dexmedetomidine) when compared to the RC group (ropivacaine + clonidine) for the administration of epidural analgesia among spine surgeries. Hence, Ropivacaine added with clonidine provides shorter duration compared with dexmedetomidine.

Milligan R et al(17) described that Levobupivacaine added with clonidine provides a longer duration of post-operative analgesia when compared with Levobupivacaine alone.

A meta-analysis by Bao-Sheng Lv et al(18) described that with a mean difference of 16.12 and 18.02, respectively, the duration of epidural analgesia was substantially greater in ROPI-SUF (Ropivacaine+sufentanil) and LBUPI-SUF (Levobupivacaine+ sufentanil) administered women than in BUPI-SUF (Bupivacaine+ sufentanil) administered women.

Therefore, the levobupivacaine added with clonidine provides longer duration of analgesia.

Hemodynamic parameters

Although, hemodynamic stability was attained by both groups of drugs, it was found that like heart rate was significantly higher in group LC than in group RC. The systolic and

diastolic blood pressure was found to be higher in group LC during two, four, and five hours of post-operative analgesia. Sharma M et al(15) reported that the hemodynamic changes showed no significant difference among epidural fentanyl & ropivacaine and epidural fentanyl & levobupivacaine.

Anusha T et al(9) found that there were no significant changes in diastolic blood pressure among levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups.

Babu S et al(16) showed that there was a decrease in heart rate and mean arterial blood pressure in the RC group (ropivacaine + clonidine) when compared to the RD group (ropivacaine + dexmedetomidine) for the administration of epidural analgesia among spine surgeries.

Burlacu C L et al(19) stated that Levobupivacaine concentration increases in epidural anaesthesia and analgesia extend sensory and motor block duration without raising the risk of unfavourable side effects. But going up to 20 mL levobupivacaine 0.75% in volume and concentration also comes with a substantial risk of hypotension, as well as delayed block regression. Continuous epidural infusion is a superior technique to manage the length and quality of levobupivacaine-induced epidural block without causing severe motor block or hemodynamic effects.

VAS score

Our study showed that the mean VAS score was significantly higher in Group RC compared with LC during two, three, four, five, and six hours of post-operative analgesia.

Sharma M et al(15) found that most patients who received epidural Ropivacaine & Fentanyl reported a rise in mean VAS after 4-5 hours, but most patients getting epidural Levobupivacaine & Fentanyl experienced this increase after 3–4 hours.

Anusha T al(9) reported that the baseline VAS score and the VAS scores at the intervals of 15, 30, and 45 minutes did not show any significant difference among both groups (levobupivacaine and ropivacaine). Meanwhile, the VAS score was significantly higher in the ropivacaine group compared with levobupivacaine during the intervals of one hour, two hours, three, five, and six hours which shows similar results to our study.

Babu S et al(16) showed that there was an increase in VAS score after four hours in the RC group (ropivacaine + clonidine) when compared to the RD group (ropivacaine + dexmedetomidine) for the administration of epidural analgesia among spine surgeries.

Levobupivacaine was often just as successful in controlling pain and was particularly useful in treating postoperative pain when paired with morphine, fentanyl, or clonidine.(20) According to Markham A et al(21), when the two medications are given at the same concentration, direct comparisons generally demonstrate that epidural ropivacaine is less effective than epidural bupivacaine. Senard M et al(22) stated that 0.1% levobupivacaine and 0.1% ropivacaine offer equivalent postoperative analgesia with a similar rate of adverse effects when administered as patient-controlled epidural analgesia in conjunction with small-dose epidural morphine.

While some studies have shown similar pain relief and hemodynamic effects between Levobupivacaine and Ropivacaine when administered via the epidural route, other studies have reported that patients receiving Ropivacaine were able to ambulate earlier than those receiving Levobupivacaine. (15)

Side effects

Anusha T et al(9) reported that nausea, shivering and vomiting were common in the RD group compared with the LD group, and urinary retention was found to be the least reported side effect in both LA groups. This result shows similar findings of our study results, anyhow dizziness was most observed in Group RC based on our findings.

Conclusion

Levobupivacaine and Ropivacaine were long-acting, well-tolerated local anesthetics, both have a similar effect on post-operative analgesia and hemodynamic parameters. The epidural levobupivacaine when combined with clonidine provides better analgesia, early time of onset, and longer duration of analgesia when compared with Ropivacaine.

Declarations

Funding: No funding source

Conflict of interest: None declared

Ethical approval: This study was registered with Institutional Human Ethical Committee

References

1. Mathew P, Aggarwal N, Kumari K, Gupta A, Panda N, Bagga R. Quality of recovery and analgesia after total abdominal hysterectomy under general anesthesia: A randomized controlled trial of TAP block vs epidural analgesia vs parenteral medications. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol*. 2019;35(2):170–5.
2. Jørgensen H, Fomsgaard JS, Dirks J, Wetterslev J, Andreasson B, Dahl JB. Effect of peri- and postoperative epidural anaesthesia on pain and gastrointestinal function after abdominal hysterectomy. *BJA Br J Anaesth*. 2001 Oct 1;87(4):577–83.
3. Raghvendra KP, Thapa D, Mitra S, Ahuja V, Gombar S, Huria A. Postoperative pain relief following hysterectomy: A randomized controlled trial. *J -Life Health*. 2016;7(2):65–8.
4. Ackroyd SA, Hernandez E, Roberts ME, Chu C, Rubin S, Mantia-Smaldone G, et al. Postoperative complications of epidural analgesia at hysterectomy for gynecologic malignancies: an analysis of the National Surgical Quality Improvement Program. *Int J Gynecol Cancer [Internet]*. 2020 Aug 1 [cited 2023 Sep 26];30(8). Available from: <https://ijgc.bmj.com/content/30/8/1203>
5. Yasaei R, Saadabadi A. Clonidine. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 [cited 2023 Sep 25]. Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK459124/>
6. Gupta S, Raval D, Patel M, Patel N, Shah N. Addition of epidural Clonidine enhances postoperative analgesia: A double-blind study in total knee- replacement surgeries. *Anesth Essays Res*. 2010;4(2):70–4.
7. van Essen EJ, Bovill JG, Ploeger EJ, Houben JJ. Pharmacokinetics of clonidine after epidural administration in surgical patients. Lack of correlation between plasma concentration and analgesia and blood pressure changes. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand*. 1992 May;36(4):300–4.
8. Rao KG, Misra S, Shukla A. Comparison between Epidural Ropivacaine versus Ropivacaine with Clonidine in Patients Undergoing Abdominal Hysterectomy: A Randomized Study. *Anesth Essays Res*. 2017 Jun;11(2):334.
9. Anusha T, Kumar K, Suggala, Tejaswi. A comparative study between 0.2% ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine and 0.125% levobupivacaine with dexmedetomidine for post-operative epidural analgesia in patients undergoing total abdominal hysterectomy. 2022. 9(1):701–5.
10. Heppolette CAA, Brunnen D, Bampoe S, Odor PM. Clinical Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics of Levobupivacaine. *Clin Pharmacokinet*. 2020 Jun;59(6):715–45.
11. Bajwa SJS, Kaur J. Clinical profile of levobupivacaine in regional anesthesia: A systematic review. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol*. 2013;29(4):530–9.
12. Silva M, Halpern SH. Epidural analgesia for labor: Current techniques. *Local Reg Anesth*. 2010 Dec 8;3:143–53.

13. Epidural Analgesia - an overview | ScienceDirect Topics [Internet]. [cited 2023 Oct 18]. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/medicine-and-dentistry/epidural-analgesia>
14. Chandrakant P, Vinod Kumar V, Arvind K, Neeraj K, Gunjan K. A Prospective Double-Blind Comparative Clinical Study Between Caudal Levobupivacaine (0.125%) with Clonidine and Ropivacaine (0.125%) with Clonidine on Post-Operative Analgesia in Paediatric Patients Undergoing Infra-Umbilical Surgery. *Romanian J Anaesth Intensive Care*. 2020 Jul;27(1):52–7.
15. Sharma M, Shahi V, Bhardwaj M, Varshney S, Sangal S. To compare the efficacy of ropivacaine with fentanyl v/s levobupivacaine with fentanyl in post-operative epidural analgesia in lower limb and lower abdominal surgeries. *Indian J Clin Anaesth*. 2019 May 15;6(2):293–7.
16. Saravana Babu MS, Verma AK, Agarwal A, Tyagi CM, Upadhyay M, Tripathi S. A comparative study in the post-operative spine surgeries: Epidural ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine and ropivacaine with clonidine for post-operative analgesia. *Indian J Anaesth*. 2013 Aug;57(4):371.
17. Milligan KR, Convery PN, Weir P, Quinn P, Connolly D. The efficacy and safety of epidural infusions of levobupivacaine with and without clonidine for postoperative pain relief in patients undergoing total hip replacement. *Anesth Analg*. 2000 Aug;91(2):393–7.
18. Lv BS, Wang W, Wang ZQ, Wang XW, Wang JH, Fang F, et al. Efficacy and safety of local anesthetics bupivacaine, ropivacaine and levobupivacaine in combination with sufentanil in epidural anesthesia for labor and delivery: a meta-analysis. *Curr Med Res Opin*. 2014 Nov;30(11):2279–89.
19. Burlacu CL, Buggy DJ. Update on local anesthetics: focus on levobupivacaine. *Ther Clin Risk Manag*. 2008 Apr;4(2):381–92.
20. Foster RH, Markham A. Levobupivacaine: a review of its pharmacology and use as a local anaesthetic. *Drugs*. 2000 Mar;59(3):551–79.
21. Markham A, Faulds D. Ropivacaine. A review of its pharmacology and therapeutic use in regional anaesthesia. *Drugs*. 1996 Sep;52(3):429–49.
22. Senard M, Kaba A, Jacquemin MJ, Maquoi LM, Geortay MPN, Honoré PD, et al. Epidural levobupivacaine 0.1% or ropivacaine 0.1% combined with morphine provides comparable analgesia after abdominal surgery. *Anesth Analg*. 2004 Feb;98(2):389–94.